

Study Protocol

Objective

To evaluate the specification and implementation of 14 requirements for a multimodal framework for User Experience (UX) evaluation in interactive Web systems.

Research Method

The research method of this study is a focus group. The focus group is a data collection and analysis technique used in qualitative research and consists of a set of people selected and brought together by researchers to discuss and comment on a topic — the research object — based on their personal experience (Gatti, 2005).

Population

For this study, 5 professionals from academia and industry with experience in the areas of Human-Computer Interaction and Software Engineering will be invited.

Materials and Resources

In this study, the following materials and resources will be used:

- Informed Consent Form (ICF);
- Profile characterization questionnaire;
- Form for evaluating the framework's requirements;
- Google Meet platform, with recording, for conducting the study.

Study Period

The study is planned to be conducted in the second half of October 2024, with a maximum duration of 10 days.

Execution Procedures

This study will consist of two stages. In the first stage, participants will be invited by email. The invitation will present the objective of the study, the ICF together with the profile characterization questionnaire, and will request availability for participation. After all participants agree to the ICF and answer the profile characterization and availability questionnaires, the form for evaluating the framework's requirements will be sent so that participants can, beforehand, make their considerations about the material that will be discussed in the focus group. This form will present the list of 14 requirements in a table followed by columns with criteria based on requirements specification and inspection techniques (correct, unambiguous, complete, consistent, ranked for importance, verifiable, modifiable, and traceable), in accordance with the IEEE Std 830-1998 standard. In the second stage, participants will meet remotely, on previously agreed dates

and times, through the Google Meet platform, to discuss each person's impressions of the list of requirements. As informed in the ICF, the session will be recorded and will last a maximum of 90 minutes. In the first part, the researchers will give a presentation about the framework and the implemented requirements to clarify any doubts the participants may have. In the second part, participants will be able to freely discuss their perceptions regarding the requirements and the framework. Upon reaching the maximum time or when the discussion topics are exhausted, the focus group will be concluded.

Data Analysis Procedures

The audio of the recorded focus group session will be transcribed in full. The text will be analyzed using open coding procedures (Corbin and Strauss, 2014). This type of coding allows the data to be analyzed, compared, and coded into categories. In this way, the researchers will be able to identify the main points addressed in the focus group and produce a synthesis of the entire discussion.

Expected Results

The aim is to obtain a synthesis of the evaluation of the specification and implementation quality of the requirements presented, verifying whether they meet the initial proposal of the framework, what needs to be corrected or improved, and whether there are other requirements to be considered.

References

Corbin, J. and Strauss, A. **Basics of Qualitative Research: Techniques and Procedures for Developing Grounded Theory**. New York, USA: SAGE Publications, 4th edition, 2014.

Gatti, B. A. **Grupo Focal na pesquisa em Ciências Sociais e Humanas** [Focus Group in Social and Human Sciences Research]. Brasília, DF: Liber Livro Editora, 2005.

IEEE Recommended Practice for Software Requirements Specifications, **IEEE Std 830-1998**, pp. 1-40, 1998.